

The dried and powdered seeds of the plant (5 Kg.) were subjected to solvent extraction with petroleum-ether (60°–80°), benzene and alcohol successively at their boiling points for 18 hr, and the different extracts were examined.

The petroleum-ether extract (90 g.) of the seeds of the plant, obtained after removal of the solvent, was neutral to litmus and gave positive Liebermann Burchard test. This extract was subjected to steam-distillation and then the residue was saponified in benzene with alcoholic KOH ($N/2$, 400 ml.) for 6 hr. The unsaponifiable matter (45 g.) was then divided into acetone-soluble and acetone-insoluble parts.

The acetone-insoluble part (1.25 g.) on chromatography (alumina), elution with petroleum-ether (60°–80°), and purification yielded a colourless product (A–350 mg), m.p. 66°. It appeared to be a paraffin; i.r. peaks at 2920, 2960 and 2850 cm^{-1} (C–H saturated); 1460, 1470 and 1375 cm^{-1} (C–CH₃); 720 and 730 cm^{-1} (CH₂)_n. Found: C, 85.0; H, 14.4%; calc. for C₃₀H₆₂: C, 85.22; H, 14.78%. But later Gas-liquid-chromatography showed it to be a mixture of *n*-alkanes (C₂₇–C₂₇) containing mainly *n*-trtriacontane (C₃₃, 36.8%); *n*-hentriacontane (C₃₁, 35%); *n*-penta-triacontane (C₃₅, 13.4%) and *n*-nonacosane (C₂₉, 7.2%). Odd numbered alkanes predominated as usual.

The acetone-soluble part (40 g.) of the petroleum-ether extract was also chromatographed over alumina. A product B (100 mg, TLC. homogeneous), m.p. 135°–36°, (α)_D²⁵ –32.5°, was obtained in shining flakes on elution with chloroform and crystallisation (methanol). It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test, yellow colour with tetra-nitro-methane and was identified as β -sitosterol by mixed-melting-point determination, co-T.L.C. with authentic specimen of the compound, and preparation of its acetate (m.p. 122°) and benzoate (m.p. 144°–6°)⁷. The benzene-extract (25 g.) of the seeds on chromatography (alumina) and crystallisation (methanol) yielded only one pure compound which was identified as β -sitosterol in the above manner.

The alcoholic extract (100 g.) obtained from the defatted seeds (4 kg.) showed the presence of carboxylic acids, phenolic products and reducing sugars. Glucose was identified in the extract by descending co-paper chromatography (Whatman filter paper No. 1) with authentic specimen of the sugar using solvent system (organic layer) consisting of *n*-butanol : water : acetic acid (4 : 5 : 1, V/v, 36 hr) and aniline phthalate as spraying reagent.

The ethanolic extract after removal of the solvent was extracted with hot water. The hot-water-soluble part (residue) was then repeatedly extracted with aq. solution of sodium carbonate (10%). The alkaline solution was acidified and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was concentrated and the residue, after removal of ether was dissolved in hot water and then treated with lead acetate solution and the precipitate thus formed was filtered. The filtrate was delead (H₂S), concentrated and the residue was crystallised from hot water. It yielded *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid (m.p. 215°–16°) identified by mixed m.p. and co-ascending-paper-chromatography

with authentic specimen using solvent system *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5, V/v; organic layer) and ferric chloride as spraying reagent⁸.

The yellow precipitate was also decomposed by H₂S, concentrated, and the residue on crystallisation (hot water) gave another acid m.p. 287°, and identified as 5-oxy-isophthalic acid (m.p. 288°, lit)⁹.

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Analytical applications of *p* NN-Bis-2 Cyanoethylamino benzaldehyde in the detection of oils. Part I

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THE role of tertiary aminobenzaldehydes particularly *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (DAB) as analytical reagents is well known. *p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde has been used in the detection of urea^{1,2} and bile pigments in urine³. Lienodo⁴ has reported the determination of blood urea levels with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde. Colour reaction of sesame oil with 2% solution of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid has been reported by Fleig⁵. Looking to the structural similarity of the *p* NN-bis-2-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde with DAB it was thought of interest to test this aldehyde for the detection of vegetable and animal oils. The aldehyde was prepared according to the method suggested by Thomas and Ittyerah⁶.

Experimental

The following procedure was adopted for the detection of oils.

To one ml of oil, first one ml of the aldehyde solution (0.4 g., in 100 ml of ethanol) and then one ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. The mixture was allowed to stand for 5 min and then warmed. The colour before and after heating was noted. Observations made are recorded in the following table :

Sl.No.	Oil	TABLE	
		Colour	
		Initial	After warming
1.	Groundnut oil	No change	No change
2.	Sesame oil	violet	violet
3.	Mahuwa oil	purple	Deep purple
4.	Mustard oil	Light pink	Pink
5.	Coconut oil	No change	No change
6.	Linseed oil	Light pink	Light pink
7.	Hydrogenated groundnut oil	No change	No change
8.	Whale oil	pink	pink
9.	Seal oil	pink	pink
10.	Cod liver oil	pink	pink
11.	Butter fat (Ghee)	No change	No change

Deep and distinct colours are developed in case of mahuwa and sesame oils and it has been observed that these oils can be detected with a very small quantity of the reagent. With these two oils the colour deepens on warming. Similar colour change has also been noticed when mahuwa or sesame oil is present as one of the components in a mixture of oils.

The possibility of the use of *p* NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-aminobenzaldehyde in the detection of sterols is being worked out.

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2,4-Dihydroxy ketones and 2,4-Dihydroxy ketoximes as indicators for the Direct CyDTA titration of Ferric ions

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MARPLE¹ showed the superior accuracy of CyDTA compared to the direct EDTA titration of iron. According to him the end point with chrome Azurol S is much more easily determined than that with thiocynate or sulphosalicylic acid. It is to be noted however, that milligram-amounts of aluminium react with chrome Azurol S to give a violet colour which obscures the end point for the iron titration. The conditions for the use of thiocynate indicator are very restrictive. According to Martinez², with sulphosalicylic acid and tiron results are high upto 4%. The present paper reports the use of 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy-propionophenone, 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone oxime and 2,4-dihydroxy propiophenone oxime as indicators for the direct titration of iron using CyDTA.

Indicator Solutions :

1% solutions were prepared in 95% ethanol. The solutions were stable upto 4 weeks.

Observations :

2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy propiophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy butyrophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone oxime, 2,4-dihydroxypropionophenone oxime and 2,4-dihydroxybutyrophenone oxime give violet colours with ferric ions. Preliminary studies indicated that 2,4-dihydroxybutyrophenone and its oxime are not satisfactory indicators; hence the remaining four compounds were investigated in detail.

Colour Change :

If solution containing ferric ions is taken in a beaker and four drops of the indicator solution were added, the solution becomes violet. There is a sharp colour change on titration with CyDTA from purple to deep yellow at the end point.

Effect of pH :

When an aliquot of Fe⁺³ is titrated with CyDTA, iron can be estimated accurately in the pH range 1.0-2.0. However, it should be noted that below pH 1.5, the colour of the solution at the end point is of a slightly lighter shade. Hence it is advisable to add slightly more indicator (about four drops).

Effect of indicator concentration :

Titrations were carried out with different concentrations of the indicator (0.5%, 0.75%, and